

Title	Author	Type	Year	Topic for FM analysis	Input CBA	Quantitative
An Analysis of the Benefits of EULYNX style Requirements Modeling for ProRail	Bui, L. N.	Paper	2013	EULYNX is using models for its functional requirement specification and for verification and validation (via model testing). However, ProRail might use models for different purposes.	Qualitative description of benefits of SysML modelling (2.2.2); Compatibility between EULYNX and Prorail (IM) requirements (4.2.4); EULYNX model benefits and its position in ProRail (11.3)	No
Feasibility Study Reference System ERTMS	Arcadis	Report	2017	How much im are ready to adopt "standardized interfaces for ETCS"	Studies on a) Traffic Management SystemsMS, b)Electronic Interlocking, c)Centralization of Traffic Control (in 5 years) (pg 21-22) studies on Short-Term versus Long-Term benefits Table 3.3 (pg 31)	No
Evaluating the effect of a lightweight formal technique in industry	Osaiweran et.al	Paper	2015	The use of lightweight formal techniques in software engineering	Survey on quality code improvements (decrease of defects) when using FM in SW development (8.1); Baseline of productivity in ASD SW development (8.2); Survey on achieved quality and productivity of industrial projects that incorporated formal methods into software development (9)	No (except cases for baseline)

Signal modernization at Stocklom Metro	Prover	Report	2019/2020	Application of computer -based interlockings	Considering maintenance work and to increase quality in general(pg 3)	No
How product development organizations can achieve long- term cost savings using MBSE	Krasner, J.	Report	2015	Controlling costs across life cycle **	Table 3.1: Comparing Cost of MBSE and non-MBSE Systems Developments (2010- 2015)	Yes
Practices for Formal Models as Documents: Evolution of VDM Application to “Mobile FeliCa” IC Chip Firmware	Taro Kurita, Fuyuki Ishikawa , and Keijiro Araki	Paper	2015	Practices for formal models/This paper reported on the latest application of VDM to the development of third-generation firmware for Mobile FeliCa IC chip	Comparison of the Second and Third Generation FM (pg 4)	No
Application of a Formal Specification Language in the Development of the “Mobile FeliCa” IC Chip Firmware for Embedding in Mobile Phone	Taro Kurita, Miki Chiba, and Yasumasa Nakatsugawa	Paper	2008	Several chip manufacturers in order to reduce risks in manufacturing and sales.	a)the extremely high quality of the software so as to avoid serious problems related to social infrastructure (pg 1)b) Table 1. Percentages of the Cause of Errors(pg 3)	No

Recent Industrial Applications of VDM in Japan	Peter Gorm Larsen	Paper	2007	This is one of the longest established model-oriented formal methods, having originated in the IBM laboratories in Vienna at the beginning of the 1970s.	Reduced cost of rework (pg 2)	No
Formal Methods: Practice and Experience	P.G.Larsen, J.C. Bicaregui, J. Woodcock, J. Fitzgerald, J.	Paper	2009	Reporting on a new survey of industrial use, comparing the situation in 2009 with the most significant surveys carried out over the last 20 years	Table 1 data collected on Applications Domain (pg 5) Fig. 6. the use of formal techniques have an effect on time, cost, and quality? (pg 10)Fig. 7. Overall satisfaction with the used of formal techniques Fig. 8. Overall satisfaction with the techniques used (pg 11)Fig. 9. Overall satisfaction with the tools used Fig. 10. Intention to use formal techniques again	Yes
The 2020 Expert Survey on Formal Methods	Garavel, H. ter Beek, M. van de Pol, J.	Survey	2020	Multi-sectorial application of FM	Expert survey on benefits of FM (page 12)	Yes
Study on the Barriers to the Industrial Adoption of Formal Methods	Davis, J. A. Clark, M. Cofer, D.	Paper	2013	The authors conducted an informal survey of contractors, customers, and certification authorities in the United States aerospace domain to identify barriers to the adoption of formal methods and suggested mitigations for those barriers	Perceived high entry cost of doing formal methods, lack of evidence of reduced cost for the second use of formal methods, psychological barriers, and skills barriers(pg 16). Formal analysis can be expensive in actual cost or measured financial risk. (5)It is time-consuming to write robust properties. (pg 9)Several projects report a savings in cost when using formal methods(pg 9)	No
Study on the Barriers to the Industrial Adoption of Formal Methods	Davis, J. A. Clark, M. Cofer, D. Fifarek, A. Hinchman, J. Hoffman, J.	Report	2010	The barriers to the adoption of formal methods, and the suggested mitigations to alleviate those barriers.	Fig. 1. Change in the Use of Formal Methods in the Last 5 Years (pg 5)	No

	Hulbert, B. Miller, S. P. Wagner, L.					
Formal Methods in Dependable Systems Engineering: A Survey of Professionals from Europe and North America	Gleirscher, M. Marmsoler, D.	Paper	2020	The use of formal methods in mission-critical software domains, examining industrial and academic views		Yes
Architecture-driven, Multi-concern and Seamless Assurance and Certification of Cyber-Physical Systems	Winkler, B.	Paper	2018	Case studies description and business impact	Table 2. Failures category of Intelligent Electronic Devices or IEDs	Yes
Report on Railway Safety and Interoperability in the EU	ERA	Paper	2018	The European Union Agency for Railway has entered a new era, with a fully-fledged package of tasks, involving the continuation of the progress with safety and interoperability, while getting ready for its role of authority for vehicle authorisations and single safety certificates.	From Figure 1- to figure 20 there is a study of the most significant railway accident Figure 51: Economic impact of significant accidents, SERA, million EUR, 2016 Figure 52: Economic impact of significant accidents, by country in SERA, million EUR, 2016 Figure 56: CAPEX per ETCS equipped vehicle (without prototype), 2011-2017	Yes
Industrial Deployment of Formal Methods: Trends and Challenges	John Fitzgerald, Juan Bicarregui, Peter Gorm Larsen, and Jim Woodcock	Paper	2009	The DEPLOY project has provided a rare opportunity to explore and document the benefits of and challenges to creating and applying formal engineering methods in industrial settings	Fig. 10.2 2012 dataset—Projects by application type Fig. 10.3 2012 dataset—Projects by formal technique used Fig. 10.6 Reported effects of use of formal methods on time, cost and quality Fig. 10.7 Perceived overall success of the use of formal methods Fig. 10.10 Intention to use formal methods again	Yes
Realising the Benefits of Formal Methods	Anthony Hall	Paper	2013	Real benefits of formal methods	Fig. 1. Evidence for the achievement of low defect rates. Fig. 2. Cost of correcting a requirements defect according to the stage at which it is discovered. Fig. 3. Progress in Reducing Defect Rates	Yes

Formal Methods for Commercial Applications Issues vs. Solutions	Saiqa Bibi, Saira Mazhar, Nasir Mehmood Minhas, Irfan Ahmed	Paper	2014	Formal methods are actually precise techniques; tools support is provided for development of software as well as hardware systems.	Figure 2. Formal approaches' effect on cost Figure 3. Less error rate during development process using formal approach Table 2. Defects are reduced with formal approaches Figure 4. Formal approaches' effect on quality Figure 5. Overall effects of formal methods in software industry	Yes
Power and Limitations of Formal Methods for Software Fabrication: Thirty Years Later	Edgar Serna M. and Alexei Serna A	Paper	2017	Formal methods had undoubted capabilities and advantages, but they also had serious limitations that prevented their widespread acceptance and adoption.	Table 1: Power and limitations of formal methods Table 3: Power and limitations of formal methods Table 4: Power and limitations of formal methods	No
Seven Myths of Formal Methods	Anthony Hall	Paper	1990	This article challenges such common myths on formal method	Myth 1 Myth 5	No
Cost Effective Use of Formal Methods in Verification and Validation	D. Richard Kuhn Ricky W. Butler	Paper	2001	This paper focuses on cost-effective applications of formal techniques in V&V, particularly recent developments such as automatic test generation and use of formal methods for analyzing requirements and conceptual models without a full-blown formal verification.	Figure 2. Applicability of formal techniques to M&S validation and verification Table 4.3. Estimated Costs of Using Automated Test Generation Under Conservative Assumptions	No
Formal methods: the very idea Some thoughts about why they work when they work	Daniel M. Berrya	Paper	2002	The paper defines formal methods (FMs) and describes economic issues involved in their application	Fig. 1. Cost to *x error as a function of detection stage. Fig. 2. Percentage cost overrun as a function of study phase cost	Yes